

A Systronic-335 digital pH meter with calibrated glass electrode and a saturated calomel separated by salt-bridge to avoid the influence of Cl^- ions, was used for pH measurements. The temperature was maintained by immersing the cell in a thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ$).

Results and Discussion

The practical proton-ligand constants ($\log K^H$) of ARS, HQ and RAPSA (sodium salt) and metal-ligand constants ($\log K_{MAL}^M$) for 1:1:1 biligand chelates evaluated by using the Irving-Rossotti technique⁷ and extension to biligand system⁸ are summarised in Table 1.

The secondary ligands ARS, HQ and RAPSA are dihydroxy, aromatic compounds. The large difference in the successive deprotonation constants of ARS and HQ was because of the stable quinonide formation due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding⁹. The secondary ligands offered (O, O) bidentate chelation¹⁰. The first step deprotonation of RAPSA probably involved deprotonation of the phenolic OH group at *para*-position to the CH_3CO group and the second step involved the deprotonation of the phenolic OH group at the *ortho*-position to the CH_3CO group as there is possibility of the intramolecular hydrogen bonding between latter OH proton with the carbonyl oxygen atom of the CH_3CO group. The secondary ligand RAPSA may act as bidentate ligand using the carbonyl oxygen of the CH_3CO group and the phenolic oxygen group at its *ortho*-position.

The order $\text{La}^{III} < \text{Nd}^{III}$ of stability constants ($\log K_{MAL}^M$) could be attributed to the decreased size and increased ionic potential of the Nd^{III} ions¹¹. The expansions of coordination sphere of metal ions could take place in case of all primary ligands except NTA. The primary chelate (MNTA) and (MHEDTA) were electrically neutral, MCYDTA and MEDTA were mono-negative and MDTPA was binegative. This lowered electrostatic attraction of MA for the secondary ligands in going from M(NTA), and this results in destabilising the biligand chelates. ΔH and ΔG for the biligand chelate formation were favourable (Table 1). ΔS values were positive, all showing chelation of the (L) with (MA) to form the biligand $[\text{M}(\text{A})-(\text{L})]$ complexes.

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Potentiometric Studies of Metal Schiff Base Chelates in Mixed Aquo-organic Solvent Systems

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LITERATURE survey reveals that the proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation equilibria in mixed solvent systems are greatly influenced by the nature of the co-solvent¹⁻⁵. With an aim to study such effects, we report in this communication, a potentiometric study of the Schiff base ligand salicylidene-2-iminopyridine and the formation of its complexes with rare earth metal ions, Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} , Sm^{III} and Gd^{III} in aquo-organic solvent systems having different dielectric constant values.

Experimental

All the chemicals and reagents used were either of A.R grade or purified before use. Double-distilled water was used throughout.

Preparation of ligand: The ligand was prepared by following the method as described in our earlier paper⁶.

Preparation of metal salt solution: Rare earth metals were converted to perchlorates by dissolving their oxides/carbonates with requisite amount of perchloric acid and evaporating it to dryness on a water-bath. The metal ions were estimated by EDTA method. The metal perchlorates were dissolved in 0.1 M HClO_4 to avoid hydrolysis.

pH-titration technique: pH-metric titration method of Bjerrum-Calvin^{5,6} as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁷ was followed to determine the formation constant values. The experimental procedure involved the titration of (i) free acid, (ii) acid + ligand and (iii) acid + ligand + metal ion solutions

with 0.5 M NaOH ($I = 0.1 M \text{ NaClO}_4$, temp. = $30 \pm 1^\circ$).

The amount of solvent and water were adjusted in each case to get the desired composition. The total volume in each case was kept constant (50 ml) initially, and a varying ratio of metal salt to ligand (1:1; 1:2; 1:3; 1:4) was maintained in different set of metal titrations.

Correction for pH measurements in different aquo-organic solvent systems was made as described by Van Uiter and Hass⁸. The dielectric constant (ϵ) values for different solvent compositions were obtained from literature^{9, 10}.

Results and Discussion

From the titration curves using the solution (i) and (ii), \bar{n}_H values at various pH values were evaluated and the formation curves were obtained. The proton-ligand stability constant $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ in different aquo-organic media were evaluated by using Bjerrum's half-integral method and point-wise calculation method¹¹; the values agree closely. The constant K_1^H refers to the association of proton to phenoxide ion ($\text{SB}^- + \text{H}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{SBH}$; SBH = Schiff base ligand) and K_2^H to the protonation of pyridine nitrogen of the Schiff base ligand ($\text{SBH} + \text{H}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{SBH}_2^+$).

The possibility of the formation of polynuclear complexes was ignored due to the very low concentration of metal ions used in the study. The metal curves show departure from the ligand curve at the pH which is much below the pH of metal hydrolysis.

From the titration curves of the solutions (ii) and (iii), \bar{n} and pL values were calculated according to the method described earlier¹². In all the metal titrations it was observed that the maximum value of \bar{n} was near about 0.8 and this indicated only 1:1 complexation. The value of metal-ligand stability constant, $\log K_1$, corresponding to metal-ligand equilibria ($\text{SBH} + \text{M} \rightleftharpoons \text{SBM} + \text{H}^+$; $\text{M} = \text{Pr}^{III}, \text{Nd}^{III}, \text{Sm}^{III}, \text{Gd}^{III}$) was obtained by Bjerrum's half-integral method by plotting \bar{n} values against pL values. The values of $\log K_1$ were also obtained graphically from the usual expression¹¹.

The formation constant values along with standard deviation (σ)¹³ determined in aquo-organic media of different compositions and reciprocal dielectric constant ($1/\epsilon$) appear in Tables 1 and 2. Studies in the water-ethanol system of varying compositions have revealed that the stability value (K_1^H) for the hydroxyl proton which is primarily ionic in character increases linearly with the increase in $1/\epsilon$. Such an increase can be explained in the light of Born's model¹⁴. On the contrary, K_2^H values show a linear decrease with the increase in $1/\epsilon$. The reason may be due to the non-electrostatic parameters like the basicity of the solvent¹⁵. However, the overall proton-ligand formation constant values (β_n^H) show a linear increase with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium.

From the metal-ligand systems studied in 50% (v/v) acetone-water, methanol-water and ethanol-water media, it has been observed that there is

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SALICYLIDENE-2-IMINOPYRIDINE IN DIFFERENT AQUO-ORGANIC SOLVENT MEDIUM

Temp. = $30 \pm 1^\circ$, $I = 0.1 M (\text{NaClO}_4)$										
Cations	Method used*	50% (v/v) acetone-water			50% (v/v) ethanol-water			50% (v/v) methanol-water		
		$\log K_1^{**}$	$\log \beta_n$	σ	$\log K_1^{**}$	$\log \beta_n$	σ	$\log K_1^{**}$	$\log \beta_n$	σ
H ⁺	H	9.20 ^a 6.42 ^b	15.64		8.97 ^a 6.50 ^b	15.51		8.58 ^a 6.35 ^b	14.95	
	P	9.19 ^a 6.45 ^b			9.03 ^a 6.52 ^b			8.60 ^a 6.38 ^b		
Pr ^{III}	H	6.15	6.11	0.078	5.10	5.10	0.063	5.06	5.05	0.064
	P	6.07			5.10			5.05		
Nd ^{III}	H	5.81	5.81	0.068	5.22	5.25	0.071	4.54	4.57	0.062
	P	5.81			5.28			4.60		
Sm ^{III}	H	5.55	5.56	0.061	5.39	5.40	0.027	4.50	4.52	0.060
	P	5.58			5.40			4.54		
Gd ^{III}	H	5.78	5.78	0.050	5.25	5.23	0.030	4.70	4.73	0.060
	P	5.78			5.21			4.75		
Reciprocal dielectric constant ($1/\epsilon$)		0.019 8			0.019 4			0.017 8		

*H = Half \bar{n} -method, P = Pointwise calculation.

**^a $\log K_1^H$, ^b $\log K_2^H$.

TABLE 2 - PROTON - LIGAND AND METAL - LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SALICYLIDENE-2-IMINOPYRIDINE IN DIFFERENT AQUO-ORGANIC SOLVENT MEDIUM

Cations	Method used*	40% (v/v) ethanol - water			30% (v/v) ethanol - water		
		log K_1^{**}	log β_n	σ	log K_1^{**}	log β_n	σ
H ⁺	H	8.80 ^a 6.65 ^b	15.44		8.70 ^a 6.62 ^b	15.30	
	P	8.88 ^a 6.55 ^b			8.68 ^a 6.60 ^b		
Pr ^{III}	H	4.60	4.60	0.068	4.45	4.45	0.012
	P	4.60			4.45		
Nd ^{III}	H	5.07	5.05	0.050	4.79	4.79	0.049
	P	5.03			4.80		
Sm ^{III}	H	5.15	5.15	0.045	4.85	4.88	0.028
	P	5.15			4.90		
Gd ^{III}	H	4.96	4.94	0.062	4.75	4.71	0.032
	P	4.93			4.67		
Reciprocal dielectric constant (1/ε)					0.017 5		
Explanation of symbols as in Table 1.					0.016 0		

no linearity between log K_1 values and the reciprocal dielectric values of different aquo-organic media. Absence of such correlation indicates that each solvent has its characteristic role, like solvation energy etc. in the interactions. However, an increasing trend in the stability values has been observed with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium. It is possible that the ionic part of the metal-ligand interactions is influenced like this by the dielectric property of the medium. The log K_1 values for the different rare earth metal ions have also been determined in ethanol-water mixture containing different proportions of ethanol (50, 40, 30%, v/v) in water. These values when plotted against 1/ε of the same aquo-organic medium having different compositions, suggested the existence of some linear relationship. The trend in the plots of log K_1 values, determined in different aquo-organic media, against e^2/r suggest the existence of some ionic character in metal-ligand bonding in accordance to Born relation¹⁶ despite the fact that these plots exhibit a slight deviation from perfect linearity. Such difference in the trend of stability values is not uncommon in the case of lanthanides and this may be due to varying degree of stabilisation arising out of interaction of 4f-metal-orbital with the ligand field¹⁷.

The order of stabilities of the metal complexes in 50% (v/v) acetone-water and methanol-water systems is Pr^{III} > Nd^{III} > Sm^{III} < Gd^{III}, and in ethanol-water (50, 40, 30%, v/v) systems it is Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} < Sm^{III} > Gd^{III}. Such observed changes in the stability order in aquo-organic media

of different dielectric constants may be due to the role played by the electrostatic and non-electrostatic parameters of the medium^{18,19}.

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